

Preventing cyberbullying through the promotion of educational intervention strategies: A case study approach

Numerous research studies have examined the phenomenon of bullying; however, the development of information and communications technology (ICT) has led to the emergence of a new type of bullying known as cyberbullying. The current research presents a case study of an internet-focused prevention programme at the Torre del Palau Institute (Institución Educativa de Educación Secundaria Torre del Palau de Terrassa), a Spanish secondary school with 627 students, from a non-experimental, qualitative perspective. The data collected from the qualitative techniques applied in this study show a holistic picture of ICT adoption enables the establishment of an institutional framework that supports prevention programmes. The results also indicate an institutional context for education in which the way that ICT adoption is approached at the teleological, psycho-pedagogical, administrative, and community levels is key for ensuring the development of cyberbullying prevention programmes.

Keywords: cyberbullying; ICT; violence in schools; Prevention program; coexistence

Introduction

In recent decades, the study of bullying has become increasingly important, especially among youth and in school contexts. From 1970 to today, four stages of bullying research can be identified, progressing from the first conceptual approximations to the application of different approaches, methodologies, and research scopes (Table 1). Like other subjects, bullying has been affected by technological innovations, especially social networks.

[INSERT TABLE 1 HERE]

Authors such as Brewer and Kerslake (2015), Peker (2015), Udris (2014), Smith (2012), and Hinduja and Patchin (2012) not only recognise the growing problem of this issue in society overall but also attach the term “cyber” to bullying when an individual or internet group uses information and communications technology (ICT) and the

communication mechanisms that it facilitates to repeatedly exert any type of aggression (physical or psychological) on others who cannot directly defend themselves.

The debate on bullying (traditional and digital) remains active at the academic and institutional levels. This argument is especially true regarding the (direct and indirect) roles of participants in bullying and their patterns of behaviour as well as the features and factors that affect and characterise them (Cuadrado-Gordillo and Fernández-Antelo, 2016).

Studies conducted in Asia, the United Kingdom, and the United States have revealed that 79% of parents and adults admitted to knowing children who have suffered from some type of cyberbullying (Asia); 17% of youth have been victims of some type of cyberbullying (United Kingdom); 87% have witnessed this type of social problem; and in the last 10 years, the rate of cyberbullying has increased in the United States, from 18.8% in 2007 to 33.8% in 2016 (McAfee, 2014; Patchin, 2016; Ditch the Label, 2017; Telenor, 2017). These figures have been subject to debate regarding the handling of statistics and the use of the methodological approaches applied to address this issue (Cook, 2017).

In the case of Spain, the first study on cyberbullying was on mid-2000 conducted by Ortega, Calmaestra, and Mora-Merchán (2008). A survey designed by Smith et al. (2006) was adapted and applied to 830 students from Córdoba (Spain). One of its main findings was the higher prevalence of this type of bullying over the internet compared with the use of mobile devices. Since then, advanced studies on cyberbullying in the country have applied a variety of methods and instruments to collect information, such as non-experimental qualitative and quantitative analysis designs that are both descriptive and inferential. This context has yielded analysis trends regarding the topic and a debate on the scope of the international results obtained through the variety of methodological approaches used until now (De Tejada, Muñoz and Izquierdo, 2018). It has also uncovered a growing awareness of this topic among youth (Giménez-Gualdo, Arnaiz and Maquilón-Sánchez, 2012) and the need to provide social mechanisms in which both they and their educators are encouraged to teach others about the risks of using ICT (Arnaiz et al., 2016). Likewise, the importance of family and educational contexts for the effective development of programmes to prevent this type of problem must be highlighted (Ortega-Barón, Buelga and Cava, 2016), as should the design of institutional prevention strategies that work not only with potential victims or aggressors but also with potential observers (i.e., witnesses; González, 2015).

Furthermore, the need to work on empathy and values in both school and family contexts should not be ignored (Montoro and Ballesteros, 2016). Moreover, better training and guidance should be ensured for teachers to be more assertive and effective in preventing cyberbullying (González, Prendes and López, 2016).

ICT and institutional interventions for the prevention of cyberbullying

The state of the legal framework and the definition of institutional mechanisms to prevent cyberbullying, internationally and in Spain, has not progressed far enough to build the consensus needed to penalise and prevent this phenomenon (Espelage and Sung, 2016). In the European Union, only Spain has achieved progress towards penalising this type of bullying (Montoro and Ballesteros, 2016). Internationally, the United States and Canada have achieved the same success, with the former adopting individual legislation in this regard (Espelage and Sung, 2016).

Despite the lack of consensus in Spain and other countries (e.g., Germany, Canada, the United States, Finland, Italy, and the United Kingdom) regarding preventing and intervening in cyberbullying at the societal level and in school settings, programmes to prevent this problem have been promoted in schools since the 1990s (Williford et al., 2012). As Garaigordobil and Martínez-Valderrey (2014) indicated, several of these programmes have focused on finding ways to reduce aggressive behaviour, increase social contexts and competencies that minimise the number of cyberbullying cases, help victims, and reduce belligerence and the number of school fights.

Authors such as Menesini, Nocentini, and Palladino (2012), Pieschl and Urbasik (2013), and Van Cleemput et al. (2014) have analysed foreign programmes aimed at preventing cyberbullying (e.g., those from Germany, Canada, Spain, the United States, Finland, and Italy). The promotion of digital citizenship and prosocial skills among youth is especially important to these programmes, as is the safe use of the internet, cybersecurity, the handling of personal information, and knowledge of intellectual property and current laws. Although these aspects can contribute to acquiring the competencies needed to mitigate this phenomenon, more exhaustive studies on this type of experience are required to gain greater knowledge of its effect on the behaviour of youth (Espelage and Sung, 2016).

Situating the case

The internet-focused prevention programme applied at the Torre del Palau Institute¹ in Spain began in the mid-1990s in an effort to promote a digital culture amongst its secondary school students by strengthening aspects of digital competencies throughout the 4 years of mandatory secondary education (*Educación Secundaria Obligatoria; ESO*).

In over 22 years of operation, this institutional project has reviewed different areas of action or thematic focal points to provide its students with appropriate content and activities for meeting the challenges intrinsic to ICT and social network innovations. The result of this continuous review process is that, since 2012, this internet-focused prevention programme has pursued its initial objective by focusing on issues related to school-based cyberbullying. This type of bullying has recently increased, from 2.5% in 2010 to 36.5% in 2016 (*Fundación Mutua Madrileña* and the ANAR Foundation, 2016).

This increase is the consequence of the effect of mobile phone consumption habits amongst youth, and the age of onset (between 12-13 years old) of cyberbullying among the members of this population, who are at the beginning of the phase of human development known as adolescence (García y Fernández, 2016; Save The Children, 2016; *Fundación Mutua Madrileña* and the ANAR Foundation, 2016).

From 2012 to 2017, the programme was conducted horizontally across all of the ESO course subjects², within three individual work environments in which different topics were addressed according to the educational level and the dimension treated (Table 2).

[INSERT TABLE 2 HERE]

Each one of the topics covered within the ESO levels (Table 2) includes the participation of social agents external to the Institute (e.g., representatives from state security agencies and information dissemination and information security agencies), as well as educators responsible for teaching the enrolled students (e.g., the administrative team, coordinators, teachers, and tutors). This pedagogy is conducted without

¹ To learn more about the educational institution that was the site of this case study, see <http://agora.xtec.cat/iestorredelpalau/>

² Catalan, Spanish, English, natural sciences, social sciences, mathematics, technology, music, and others

overlooking the use of the digital tools that facilitate dealing with the different topics addressed³ and through content produced by students throughout the programme (e.g., guides for using social networks).

At the institutional level exist group reflections (e.g., face-to-face formats such as assemblies and debates as well as online formats such as the forums on the Institute's platform), established in committees and school actors, in accordance with the Institute's bylaws (2017):

- An ICT committee will be comprised of the management team, the IT coordinator, and representatives of the teaching staff involved in the relevant projects of this Institute.
- The coordinators for each ESO level are responsible for explaining the activities that address the programme topics to the teachers and students, among other things.
- Tutors, responsible for programme functions related to teaching the students under their charge.
- The teaching staff support the tutors' work knowing significant information about each student under their responsibility.

The activities assigned to the aforementioned educators are supported by *ad hoc* bodies created at the institutional level that mediate and act upon the inappropriate use of ICT or cyberbullying cases, as follows:

- A discipline or coexistence committee (families, students, and teachers) will be responsible for studying cases of inappropriate internet use or school bullying that, due to their significance, require disciplinary action.
- An arbitration service (professors and ESO students)⁴ who act as arbitrators in cases that might require disciplinary action by the Centre.

³ For example, all those tips, activities and recommendations offered by specific websites such as INCIBE (<https://www.incibe.es/>), CESICAT (<https://ciberseguretat.gencat.cat/ca/inici>), Pantallas Amigas (<http://www.pantallasamigas.net/>) and others extracted from social networks that advise experts on this subject.

⁴ Using the arbitration service is voluntary for students that believe that, in the event of a conflict, their intervention could be useful.

Material and methods

The general objective of this study was to understand the type of institutional setting that helps to reduce the number of cyberbullying cases in the Spanish educational system through the promotion of internet-focused prevention programmes.

The proposed topic was approached from a non-experimental, qualitative perspective that was applied to the specific case study of the internet-focused prevention programme at the Torre del Palau Institute in Spain (*Institución Educativa Torre del Palau de Terrassa*), as a result of the following criteria:

- The public nature of this Educational Centre and the socioeconomic profiles of the students' families provide for an interesting analysis because they enable an understanding of the applicability of internet-focused cyberbullying prevention projects in geographical areas characterised by high unemployment with a history of immigration, a business environment dominated by small firms, and a high percentage of families in the medium-low per capita income stratum (Muñoz, 2003, Terrassa City Council, 2015).
- Its pioneering character related with the implementation of programmes aimed at strengthening digital skills in Spain⁵, with more than 20 years of experience in this field at the secondary and post-compulsory educational (i.e., baccalaureate) levels.
- The long term implementation of the programme taken as a study case, more than 5 years of experience, within the institution studied.

The study was conducted using three collection and analysis techniques. First, a content analysis was performed on the 2017 activities of the Centre's Educational Project (PEC). This analysis enabled the identification of how its digital adoption process is conceived, accepted, and approached as well as whether this process might help the implementation of similar programmes. To meet this goal, the following four components established by Arellano et al. (2015) were applied:

⁵ The promotion of programmes to integrate and strengthen ICT in this institution began more than a decade before the launch of national initiatives by Spain's Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport such as the School 2.0 Programme (<http://www.ite.educacion.es/eu/escuela-20>). For more information, see: <https://www.educaciontrespuntocero.com/experiencias/ecoproyeccion-en-el-instituto-torre-del-palau/27888.html>

- The teleological component analyses the expected profiles of teachers, students, and graduates. It also analyses the institutional vision and mission, objectives, indicated educational or training goals, and the principles set forth in this document.
- The psycho-pedagogical component, or the curricular and pedagogical foundations of the document, were analysed through the approach to ICT regarding the standards, objectives, and competencies to be developed through the curriculum, among other aspects.
- The administrative component analyses the monitoring, evaluation, and improvement activities for ICT skills training amongst teachers.
- The community component was related to institutional participation in a national programme for the acquisition and use of ICT, alliances, and the management of institutional ICT agreements at the educational level; and the use of technology to communicate and collaborate amongst schools, staff, parents, students, and the general community.

Each of the components analysed for the PEC was assigned a score that helped to categorise the above attributes (in partial or full) or their absence. An absence of mentions was assigned 1 point, a partial mention (i.e., an indirect or general reference) was assigned 2 points, and an explicit mention was given a score of 4. The score was averaged for each component analysed to obtain an overall average grade that served as a general reference for what is presented here.

A content or documentation analysis is one of the most important research techniques in social science and education because it enables the objective, systematic, and quantitative description of the documents studied (Martínez, 2013; Rifle, Lacy and Fico, 2014).

The second step was a documentation analysis of the disciplinary cases related to cyberbullying over the last 5 years that occurred within the educational institution used as a case study. This procedure was conducted to better understand the evolution of this phenomenon during the final years of the internet-focused prevention programme.

The third step was to complete questionnaires and conduct in-depth interviews with an intentional, non-probability sample composed of 17 students at the 4th ESO level (N = 90 students), three tutors, and the teacher-coordinator of the level for a total of four

professors ($N = X$) who were a part of the internet-focused prevention programme over the last 5 years. This procedure was conducted to better understand the assessments and recommendations of these actors regarding the institutional and training framework promoted by the aforementioned programme to reduce cyberbullying cases within the Spanish educational system.

Findings

To understand the process of ICT adoption and its effect on the development of the programme, it is first necessary to know how this process was conceived, accepted, and approached by educational institutions.

The analysis of the Torre del Palau Institute's PEC (Figure 1) reveals a situation (3.75/4.00 points) in which ICT adoption and its potential effect on training to develop digital skills and competencies amongst the students were supported by a holistic institutional setting in the terms set forth by Aviram (2002). Namely, an institutional framework that likely supported ICT adoption and the consequent development of programmes such as the one studied here. This procedure was conducted through the appropriation of knowledge and the transformation of systematic (traditional and routine) practices related to the reflection on and determination of needed changes in the psycho-pedagogical, administrative, and teleological framework required for the aforementioned purposes. Moreover, our case study found less progress with regard to the community component.

Figure 1. General analysis of the PEC by component according to the average score obtained at the Torre del Palau Institute

[INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE]

Source: Prepared by the author from the data collected and analysed from the PEC as well as institutional documents accessed during the study upon which this work was based

Note: The measurement scale used has four possible scores: 4 points (explicit mention of the aspects considered in the analysed component); 2 points (partial mention of the aspects considered in the analysed component); and 1 point (no mention of the aspects considered in the analysed component).

The value shown in each component is the total average score (\bar{x}), obtained from the summation and calculation of the average observed for each component during the analysis of the PEC and other institutional documents used to develop this paper.

For the teleological component, the PEC scored a maximum of 3.75/4.00 points as a result of the exposure of elements (principles, educational or training goals, objectives, mission, vision, and teacher and student profiles) that explicitly referred to a knowledge society (KS), to the societal development furthered by ICTs, or both.

Throughout this important document, the following goals are discussed:

- To educate using new forms of knowledge based on the selective handling of information
- To search for mechanisms that ensure the training required by a KS
- To foster innovation through the teaching provided at this educational centre based on a deep, methodological reflection and the monitoring of the results and levels of achievement of the established curricular objectives
- To train students to function in an increasingly global world and to be prepared for the challenges of the KS from the point of view of learning as well as the humanistic values required for that purpose
- To promote teachers⁶ with the necessary basic training as well as the willingness and interest to improve their work through continuous training

The only area where partial evidence was identified in the teleological component concerned the profile of the teaching centre's graduates. These individuals received a more general institutional training, which is not a reason to ignore the need to accept the inherent challenges of the KS.

The PEC analysis yielded the highest possible score (4/4 points) for both the psycho-pedagogical and administrative components, which reflects the explicit mention of:

- Administrative, pedagogical, and investigative activities; documents (e.g., the "Organisation and Functioning of the Centre" and the "Curriculum"); and institutional and communication spaces (e.g., web portals, blogs, chats, and videoconferences).
- Standards and competencies that students must attain
- Technology programmes promoted

⁶ Teachers are directly assigned by the Catalanian government's Department of Education.

- Roles and activities developed by the different educational agents that are part of the Teaching Centre (to mention a few aspects)

The aforementioned list reveals an institutional framework committed to the assimilation of its students into the KS and the dynamics of ICTs. This procedure facilitates the management and development of programmes such as the internet-focused prevention programme as well as enables an exhaustive approach to especially relevant issues that result from the contemporary digital environment such as cyberbullying.

The only component within the PEC that obtained a lower score was the community component (3.33/4.00 points). This result is due to the lack of any explicit mention of this component and to the lack of on-going ICT-related programmes and activities in an educational context with public and private sector collaboration. This lack does not necessarily depend on the educational agents connected to our case study; rather, it depends on external conditions that most likely have a greater effect on alliances with academic actors (e.g., universities and external work groups), activities (e.g., workshops to disseminate information about technological experiences with educators from the Teaching Centre and social organisations based in Terrassa, Spain), and use of ICT for communication and collaboration (e.g., the use of email and social networks) amongst schools, staff, parents, and other members of the educational community. The holistic ICT adoption scenario that was determined through the content analysis applied to the PEC case study enables the formation of an institutional framework that likely supports the implementation of programmes such as the internet-focused prevention programme analysed in the current study, especially with regard to the organisational and educational search for mechanisms that will help to avoid cases of cyberbullying among students.

Figure 2 illustrates the number of disciplinary cases related to the inappropriate use of ICT⁷ over the last 5 years versus the number of disciplinary cases related to cyberbullying (e.g. the creation of a web pages that disclose alleged personal intimacies or that insult colleagues or teachers of the Centre; and publication of photos of

⁷ The cases were categorized as follows: use of mobile devices to access websites and social networks at unauthorized times or places in the Centre; mobile device theft; intentional damage of equipment; recording conversations and taking photographs of teachers without explicit authorization; and computer-based attacks on the Centre among others.

colleagues on social networks without their consent). The data recorded by the Institute's disciplinary committee allow us to estimate the scope of the problems addressed in this Centre. Generally, the average number of cyberbullying cases was 0.6 compared with 11.8 disciplinary cases for inappropriate use of ICT during the period of active participation amongst the students and teachers involved in the study. Namely, only 5.08% of all ICT-related disciplinary cases were for cyberbullying. In other words, for every 10 ICT-related disciplinary cases, there were only 0.5 cases concerning some kind of cyberbullying amongst students.

In general, we consider that

- The average number of students enrolled in the entire Educational Centre was 672 students. As such, the average rate of cyberbullying cases was 0.44 during these 5 years (i.e., 0.06 cases per 100 students).
- Between 2013 and 2016, the average rates of cyberbullying cases nationally and within the autonomous community of Catalonia were 23.9% and 10.3%, respectively. These values are clearly higher than those observed at the Centre during the same period using the reference data from the study conducted by the ANAR Foundation and *Fundación Mutua Madrileña* (2017).

Figure 2. Disciplinary cases related to the inappropriate use of ICT versus cyberbullying between 2013 and 2017

[INSERT FIGURE 2 HERE]

Source: Created by the authors based on the Torre del Palau Institute disciplinary case report

Note: According to the official records of the Centre, each of case classified as cyberbullying occurred only once during these 5 years.

Regarding the assessments of students participating in the internet-focused prevention programme, the questionnaires allowed for the identification of two types of students. The first type (76% of respondents) shared a retrospective view that everything taught

in this type of programme is favourable because these respondents believed that it has enabled them to become more aware of and acquire a general understanding of this issue and of the dangers inherent to social networks and current digital settings. The second type (24%) shared a view that was either negative or critical because they considered the topic to be repetitive or addressed their four years of active participation in this type of programme in a basic manner.

I have learned how to avoid it and how to use the internet safely as well as how to help identify it - Student interviewee no. 16.

Well, cyberbullying is a very serious matter that must end. The victims have a very bad time and are scared, whereas the people responsible for this has a good time making another person's life impossible - Student interviewee no. 1.

We've had several talks about this over the four years, but they are always repetitive - Student interviewee no. 11.

More than 80% of the students who participated in this study recognised the practical use of the tools and concepts learned in the prevention programme regarding cyberbullying. Those students who did not complained about the low use of equipment and technology resources or had developed habits (outside of school) to counteract the effect of this type of bullying.

Personally, I always acted appropriately, so I haven't changed anything - Student interviewee no. 11.

Well, you have to be careful on social networks. One must be cautious to avoid becoming a victim of cyberbullying - Student interviewee no. 1.

I've learned the difference between saying something in person and on my mobile, where perhaps someone doesn't understand the joke - Student interviewee no. 10.

The strategies or daily habits revealed by the surveyed students can be classified into three distinct groups. The first and largest group (more than 65% of respondents) alluded to individual measures and actions for the more conscientious use of current digital settings and the management of the devices used to access the internet. The

second group (approximately 29% of respondents) showed a more passive attitude towards establishing guidelines for appropriate internet behaviour and use of technology and even seem to relate cyberbullying to the presence or absence of social networks. The last and smallest group (6% of the respondents) expressed the need to talk to their parents and notify authorities (e.g., the police) when they begin to experience this type of situation.

I have never been a cyberbullying victim, but if I was, the first thing I would do would be to discuss it with my parents, and if it gets worse, notify the police - Student interviewee no. 4.

I'm not concerned about this since I don't become involved in things that might make me a cyberbullying target - Student interviewee no. 5.

The truth is that I don't have any strategies for this since, to avoid problems, I don't use any social networks - Student interviewee no. 1.

I keep my networks private every day so that only my friends can see my profile - Student interviewee no. 13.

Don't speak to strangers and just ignore any threats or insults on the networks, and then block them - Student interviewee no. 16.

Regarding the possible improvements in the ways to address cyberbullying that have resulted from the internet-focused prevention programme, only a small percentage of students (24% of the total intentional sample) believe that the existing current measures are sufficient. The others believe that a need exists for a more active approach to cyberbullying such as implementing more participation amongst teachers and a more comprehensive treatment of the issue throughout all of the ESO courses. This treatment should include a programmatic review of all topics to improve the clarity and understanding of the measures regarding cyberbullying and students. In addition, a need exists to implement more active learning methodologies to address the different issues raised by the prevention programme. This change would facilitate not only a closer teacher-student relationship but also a more open dialogue on cyberbullying. Likewise, it would facilitate the implementation of more dynamic and collaborative training

processes to allow for more personalised and immediate monitoring of the understanding, awareness, and occurrence of potential cyberbullying cases, both in the classroom and throughout the Educational Centre.

They should implement dynamic workshops among the students with activities so that it's not so tedious – Student interviewee no. 2.

I would recommend being more aware of the students' attitudes or more aware of the students' activities to detect any issue or to help without resorting to calling the police - Student interviewee no. 4.

Even just a little discussion in class is useful for some students to understand the possible repercussions of being a cyberbully - Student interviewee no. 10.

Speak openly and clearly in the courses to clear up problems among schoolmates - Student interviewee no. 15.

From the first year in ESO, they should be creating awareness of what it is and how to prevent it; then, go deeper into the subject with each school year - Student interviewee no. 10.

Regarding the teachers, the in-depth interviews conducted with them revealed a favourable assessment of the potential effect of programmes such as the one studied. This result is especially true if the intent is to foster a school environment aimed at reducing cyberbullying cases in the educational contexts. This favourable assessment was a result of 1) the programme's innovative character in the absence of similar initiatives in Spain; 2) the execution of the programme throughout all ESO grades; 3) the experiential learning produced by the students' thought-provoking dynamics and analyses during the topics addressed; and 4) the support provided by the Centre's management in fostering information-sharing settings that support learning and the continuous contemplation of everything related to cyberbullying.

Similar initiatives are needed throughout the Spanish educational system - Teacher interviewee 2.

The administration has enabled the sharing of articles, experiences, and published analyses on cyberbullying among educators - Teacher interviewee 2.

The participation of students in this programme, from the 1st year of ESO, guarantees a greater effect of this type of initiative due to the approach to the issues throughout this academic level - Teacher interviewee 1.

The case studies coming from the students (from their personal experiences or contributed by their friends or families) are learning moments with a heavy educational effect - Teacher interviewee 3.

Regarding recommendations related to the programme, teachers emphasize the need to always be up-to-date and to constantly review and reflect (e.g., periodic internal meetings and the participation of networks of educational centres to share information on cyberbullying) on the programme topics to ensure its relevance. However, they also insisted on maintaining continuous training strategies (e.g., peer training and training throughout the academic year) and the presence of the teacher advisor role who is responsible for helping other teachers with questions or problems throughout the process.

A continuous review and updating of the internet-focused prevention programme is needed in order to maintain a relevant and adequate understanding of the issues addressed - Teacher interviewee 1.

The management team must conduct peer training and specific meetings for new teachers to ensure the successful execution of the programme throughout the school year and assign a teacher advisor to help with any questions or problems - Teacher interviewee 2.

The networks of centres that share information on cyberbullying enhance the project - Teacher interviewee 3.

Conclusions

The understanding of an institutional setting that can support the implementation of programmes to prevent cyberbullying in schools is key, especially considering the current academic, institutional, and social interest in this social problem. Likewise, it is

important to achieve progress towards identifying the elements that contribute to a better understanding of the profile and roles of the aggressors, observers, and victims; the factors that influence cyberbullying; and the socio-educational context that can facilitate the application of this type of educational programme.

The current results indicate an institutional context for education in which the way that ICT adoption is approached at the teleological, psycho-pedagogical, administrative, and community levels is key to ensuring the implementation of cyberbullying prevention programmes. Therefore, it might be useful to better understand the institutional scenarios in which prevention programmes are conducted in the field of education, such as those analysed by Menesini, Nocentini and Palladino (2012), Pieschl and Urbasik (2013) and Van Cleemput et al. (2014), among others, especially when considering that the programme featured in this case study has more than 20 years of continuous operation, and it has been able to achieve particularly high levels of ICT adoption through the PEC as well as a significant reduction in cyberbullying cases over the last 5 years compared with the levels observed for Spain overall (although this relationship will need to be analysed more thoroughly in future research).

The programme's curriculum structure and dynamic work plan execution is closely related to programmes that have experienced more frequent incidences of cyberbullying in educational environments (Espelage and Sung, 2016; Van Cleemput et al., 2014). This fact supports the idea of preventing this type of social problem through initiatives that not only have an institutional structure adapted to the intrinsic challenges of ICT but also 1) provide different types of work, discussion, and support scenarios as well as guidance and training for students, teaching and administrative staff, parents, and members of the community; and 2) consider an agenda of topics that encourages a conceptual understanding of and recommendations regarding cyberbullying as well as helps in the acquisition of prosocial and digital citizenship skills amongst youth while also strengthening the technical skills needed for the appropriate use of ICT among youth (note that this goal must be met throughout all ESO levels). These traits are valued positively by both teachers and students alike because, beyond the innovative nature of the programme, they highlight its utility with regard to learning and the practical applicability of the programme.

In addition, teachers and students highlight the need for this type of initiative to actively address and continuously review the topics, the teaching-learning

methodologies, the personalised monitoring mechanisms for the students, and the continuous training strategies designed for the personnel responsible for this type of programme (González, Prendes, López, 2016). In summary, the above strategies end up as the operational foundation for the potential success of this type of initiative, along with the institutional framework that surrounds them.

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